

**ON ASYMPTOTIC STRUCTURE OF CRITICAL MARKOV BRANCHING
 PROCESSES WITH POSSIBLY INFINITE VARIANCE**

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We consider the Markov Branching Process to be the homogeneous continuous-time Markov chain $\{Z(t), t \geq 0\}$ with state space $S_0 = \{0\} \cup S$, where $S \subset \mathbb{N}$ and $\mathbb{N} = \{1, 2, K\}$. The transition probabilities of the process

$$P_{ij}(t) := \mathbf{P} \{Z(t) = j | Z(0) = i\}$$

satisfy the following branching property:

$$P_{ij}(t) = P_{ij}^{i*}(t) \text{ for all } i, j \in S,$$

where the asterisk denotes convolution. Herein transition probabilities $P_{1j}(t)$ are expressed by relation

$$P_{1j}(t) = \delta_{1j} + a_j e^{-\Gamma t} + o(e^{-\Gamma t}) \text{ as } t \rightarrow \infty,$$

where δ_{ij} is Kronecker's delta and $\{a_j\}$ are intensities of individuals' transformation that $a_j \geq 0$ for $j \in S_0 \setminus \{1\}$ and

$$0 < a_0 < -a_1 = \sum_{j \in S_0 \setminus \{0\}} a_j < \Gamma.$$

The process $\{Z(t)\}$ was defined first by Kolmogorov and Dmitriev [4]; for more detailed information see [1, 2].

Defining generating functions $F(t; s) = \sum_{j \in S_0} P_{1j}(t) s^j$ and $f(s) = \sum_{j \in S_0} a_j s^j$ for $s \in [0, 1)$ we keep on the critical case that is $f'(1-) = 0$ and, assume that the infinitesimal generating function $f(s)$ has the representation

$$f(1 - y) = yL(y) \quad [f_n]$$

for $y \in (0, 1]$ with $L(y) = y^n L(1/y)$, where $0 < n \leq 1$ and $L(\cdot)$ is slowly varying (SV) function at infinity (in sense of Karamata); see [3, 5]. Note that the function $yL(y)$ is positive and tends to zero and has a monotone derivative so that $yL'(y)/L(y) \sim n$ as $y \rightarrow 0$; see [3, p. 401]. Thence it is natural to write

$$\frac{yL\check{y}}{L(y)} = n + d(y), \quad [L_a]$$

where $d(y)$ is continuous and $d(y) \rightarrow 0$ as $y \rightarrow 0$.

Let $R(t;s) := 1 - F(t;s)$. Sevastyanov [6] proved that if $f\check{y}(1-) < \Gamma$ then

$$\frac{1}{R(t;s)} - \frac{1}{1-s} = \frac{f\check{y}(1-)}{2}t + O(\ln t)$$

as $t \rightarrow \Gamma$ for all $s \in [0, 1)$; see [6, p. 72]. The following lemma is an essentially improvement of Sevastyanov's result.

Lemma. *Under the conditions $[f_n]$ and $[L_a]$*

$$\frac{1}{L(R(t;s))} - \frac{1}{L(1-s)} = nt + \int_0^t d(R(u;s))du.$$

If in addition $d(y) = L(y)$ then

$$\frac{1}{L(R(t;s))} - \frac{1}{L(1-s)} = nt + \frac{1}{n} \ln n(t;s) + o(\ln n(t;s))$$

as $t \rightarrow \Gamma$, where $n(t;s) = L(1-s)nt + 1$.

From this Lemma we obtain the following two limit theorems.

Theorem 1. *Let conditions $[f_n]$, $[L_a]$ hold and $d(y) = L(y)$. Then*

$$\mathbf{P}\{Z(t) > 0\} = \frac{N(t)}{(nt)^{1/n}} - \frac{\ln[a_0nt + 1]}{n^3 t} + o\left(\frac{\ln t}{t}\right)$$

as $t \rightarrow \Gamma$, where $N(t)$ is the SV-function satisfying a condition

$$N^n(t) \sim \frac{(nt)^{1/n}}{N(t)} \quad s \rightarrow 1, \quad \text{as } t \rightarrow \Gamma.$$

Theorem 2. *Let conditions $[f_n]$, $[L_a]$ hold and $d(y) = L(y)$. Then*

$$(nt)^{1+1/n} P_{11}(t) = \frac{N(t)}{a_0} - \frac{1+n}{n^3} \frac{\ln[a_0nt + 1]}{t} + o\left(\frac{\ln t}{t}\right)$$

as $t \rightarrow \Gamma$, where the SV-function $N(t)$ is defined in Theorem 1.

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